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ANALYSIS OF THE LAWS OF BALANCED THERMODYNAMICS IN HIGHER PHYSICS EDUCATION

O. Khimmatkulov, M.J. Botirova

Tashkent State Technical University

***Abstract.** The article describes the analysis of reversible and irreversible processes occurring in nature in the study of the laws of balanced thermodynamics using simple examples. It is noted that the first law of thermodynamics is the law of conservation of energy in heat processes and does not indicate the direction of processes. The concepts of entropy and thermodynamic probability are explained. It was analyzed that the second principle of thermodynamics defined by the concept of entropy shows the direction of processes.*

***Keywords:** equilibrium and quasi-static states, reversible and irreversible processes, entropy, thermodynamic probability, closed system.*

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the teaching of physics in higher educational institutions, students have an idea about the unique scientific view of the universe, which, in turn, plays an important role in mastering the professional knowledge of the specialty and putting it into practice.

It is of great importance to explain to students the essence of the classical balanced laws of thermodynamics in teaching thermodynamics of physics. Because the real processes that occur in closed systems in nature are irreversible, the second law of thermodynamics, defined by the concept of entropy, shows the direction of these processes. In teaching the basics of thermodynamics, it is required to explain to students the physical and statistical meanings of the concepts of equilibrium state, thermodynamic probability, and entropy in closed systems using simple examples. This article is devoted to the discussion of the above-mentioned issues.

MAIN PART

Classical thermodynamics is a branch of physics that studies equilibrium processes occurring in closed systems and their general laws. The state of thermodynamic equilibrium is defined as the state that is established in the system over time under conditions of constant external influence and when the temperature of the external system remains constant.

Classical thermodynamics is based on its two laws. The first law represents the law of conservation and circulation of energy in thermal processes. The second law of thermodynamics determines the direction of processes. When a thermodynamic system is in equilibrium, the thermodynamic parameters (for example, T and R) have the same value at all points in the system.

If a change occurs in the system, the internal relaxation process occurs and the state of equilibrium is restored. For example, when an ideal gas is compressed or expanded, the internal relaxation process, consisting of collisions between molecules, quickly restores equilibrium. In this case, the relaxation time is on the order of the free running time of molecules, i.e. 10^{-7} c.

In the new equilibrium state, the thermodynamic parameters change but are again the same at all points. If the gas compression or expansion process is very slow, and the time of each elemental compression or expansion process is greater than the relaxation time, a new equilibrium will be established in the system during this microprocessor. In this case, the whole process can be considered as a sequence of elementary processes in each of which intermediate balanced states are determined. If during processes the system passes through a series of equilibrium situations, such processes are called quasi-static (close to equilibrium) processes. If the process occurs equally in forward and reverse directions, that is, in both directions, the system passes through the same intermediate states, and in these processes, the system and the surrounding bodies return to their original state, such processes are called reversible processes. Any process that does not satisfy these conditions is irreversible.

Processes occurring in systems affected by conservative forces are reversible. For example, a perfectly elastic ball in free fall in a vacuum will hit a perfectly elastic metal plate and return to the initial point, passing through all the intermediate states during the fall. At the end of the process, the sphere and all surrounding objects return to their original state. Quasi-static thermal processes are also reversible. But there are no strict conservative systems and quasi-static processes in nature, because in all systems resistance forces act and processes occur at a certain speed. All real processes in nature are irreversible processes.

For example, suppose that half of a container divided by a barrier is filled with oxygen and the other half with nitrogen gas. If the barrier is removed, the gases will mix due to diffusion and both types of molecules will be evenly distributed throughout the volume of the container. The diffusion process is irreversible, and the reverse process, that is, the separation of molecules from their original state, does not occur in practice. Experiments and observations show that heat exchange is also an irreversible and unidirectional process. Heat is always transferred from a body with a higher temperature to a body with a lower temperature. The reverse process, that is, heat does not spontaneously transfer from a body with

a low temperature to a body with a high temperature. The mechanical energy of a body stopped under the influence of friction is automatically converted into the internal energy of the body, but the internal energy is not automatically converted into mechanical energy.

These processes can be explained using the concepts of molecular statistics. To do this, let's imagine the following experiment. Let's put 8 white balls in one half and 8 black balls in the other half in an orderly manner. Let each of these balls be labeled, for example, white balls have a, b, c, d, e, f, m, n, and black balls have $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \sigma, \varepsilon, \lambda, \nu$

If we start mixing balls by moving the container, black balls will appear on the left side of the container, and white balls will appear on the right side. Distribution state 1, depicted in the figure, is realized in only one way, and its thermodynamic probability is the smallest. For example, let there be 5 white and 3 black balls in the left half of the container at a certain moment. Using the $C_n^k = \frac{n!}{(n-k)!k!}$ formula, we calculate how many combinations of the given 2nd distribution state can be formed. The number of combinations in choosing $k=5$ of the $n=8$ white balls on the left side:

equal to $C_8^5 = \frac{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5} = \frac{6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} = 56$. For example, (a,b,c,d,e); (b,c,d,e,f); (c, d, e, f, m); (d,e,f,m,n); (a,c,d,e,f); (a,b,c,d,e) and so on.

The number of combinations of choosing 3 black balls moving to the left from the 8 black balls on the right:

$C_8^3 = \frac{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} = \frac{6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} = 56$. For example, ($\alpha\beta\gamma$); ($\alpha\gamma\delta$); ($\alpha\delta\sigma$); ($\alpha\sigma\varepsilon$); ($\alpha\varepsilon\lambda$); ($\alpha\lambda\nu$); ($\beta\gamma\delta$); ($\beta\delta\sigma$); ($\beta\sigma\varepsilon$) etc.

So, the distribution condition on the left side can be created by $C_8^5 C_8^3 = (C_8^5)^2 = 56^2 = 3136$ methods. For example, (a, α ,b,c, β ,d, γ ,e); (b, λ ,d,f, ε ,m, δ ,n) and so on.

Similarly, if we count the number of combinations of choosing 4 white balls moving to the right and 4 black balls moving to the left from the 8 white balls on the left

$$C_8^4 = \frac{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4} = 70. \quad \text{Such a state of distribution can be created using}$$

$$C_8^4 C_8^4 = (C_8^4)^2 = 70^2 = 4900 \text{ methods.}$$

The thermodynamic probability of a state of an arbitrary system refers to the number of different combinations of elements that create this state, that is, the number of ways.

So the thermodynamic probability of the last state we see is 4900. In the same way, we can calculate and analyze the thermodynamic probabilities of the remaining states.

Calculations show that a system of 8 white and as many black balls can be in 9 different states. The state with the greatest thermodynamic probability corresponds to the evenly distributed and most disordered state of the spheres in the container. The least likely state is the fully ordered, i.e. unmixed, state of the spheres, which can only be realized in one way. As a result of mixing, the balls are placed randomly in the parts of the container, and in general, any combination can appear. However, there are many cases where the thermodynamic probability is the greatest. The mixing of spheres is an irreversible process, and the initially ordered state of the spheres during mixing is practically impossible.

Because it is spontaneous for balls to move from a low-probability state to a high-probability state, but balls do not spontaneously move from a high-probability disordered state to a low-probability ordered state. Thus, the thermodynamic probability serves as a directional characteristic of processes. However, calculating the thermodynamic probability of a system consisting of many particles (molecules) is a very difficult problem. Therefore, in thermodynamic calculations, the quantity called entropy, which was introduced to science by Clausius, is used. Entropy, like thermodynamic probability, is a quantity that characterizes the direction of processes in nature.

According to the Boltzmann formula, entropy is proportional to the logarithm of the thermodynamic probability, i.e. $S = k \ln W$. Here S -entropy, k -Boltzmann constant, W -thermodynamic probability. If the system goes from one state to another, the change in entropy $\Delta S = S_2 - S_1 = k \ln W_2 - k \ln W_1 = k \ln$ is calculated using the expression

Since the thermodynamic probability increases in irreversible processes ($W_2 / W_1 > 1$), the entropy also increases. The entropy of the system does not change in reverse processes, that is, $\Delta S = 0$. According to the second law of thermodynamics described by Clausius, the entropy of the system does not decrease in any processes occurring in closed systems, i.e. $\Delta S \geq 0$.

A quasi-static isothermal process is a reversible process. For example, let's consider a closed system consisting of gas, load, and environment under the piston. If the gas takes some Q -heat from the environment and does some work in raising the load by expansion, the entropy change of the system is $\Delta S = \Delta S_1 + \Delta S_2 + \Delta S_3$. Here, $\Delta S_1 = \frac{Q}{T}$ is the change in entropy of the gas, and $\Delta S_2 = -\frac{Q}{T}$ is the change in

the entropy of the external environment (we consider the sign of the given amount of heat to be negative). The entropy of a conservative mechanical system consisting of a piston and a load does not change, i.e. $\Delta S_3=0$. Then $\Delta S = \frac{Q}{T} - \frac{Q}{T} + 0 = 0$. The irreversibility of the gas diffusion process can be explained by the example of the distribution of balls in a container. Due to friction, the mechanical energy of the body is converted into internal energy. In this case, the molecules of the moving body are in orderly motion in one direction, and the thermodynamic probability or entropy of this state is small. When a body stops, its mechanical energy of orderly movement is converted into the energy of disordered heat movement of the molecules of rubbing bodies, i.e., internal energy. The thermodynamic probability or entropy of a state of disordered motion is greater. Therefore, entropy increases during the transformation of mechanical energy into internal energy. Since the entropy decreases in the reverse process, the internal energy does not spontaneously convert into mechanical energy. Therefore, it is impossible to create a second type of perpetual motion machine, which works with only one heat source, for example, which works at the expense of the internal energy of surrounding bodies (earth, water, etc.). In an insulated closed system consisting of hot and cold bodies, heat is transferred from a hot body to a cold body. If the amount of transferred heat is Q –, then the entropy change of the system is $\Delta S = \Delta S_1 + \Delta S_2$. Here, $\Delta S_1 = -\frac{Q}{T_1}$ is the change in entropy of a hot body; $\Delta S_2 = \frac{Q}{T_2}$ is the change in entropy of a cold body. Total entropy change as $T_1 > T_2$: $\Delta S = \frac{Q}{T_2} - \frac{Q}{T_1} = \frac{T_1 - T_2}{T_1 T_2} Q > 0$

So entropy increases in this process. Heat from a cold body does not transfer spontaneously (without doing work) to a hot body. Because entropy decreases in this reverse process, that is, $\Delta S = \frac{Q}{T_1} - \frac{Q}{T_2} = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 T_2} Q < 0$. The first law of thermodynamics does not deny this reverse process. Because, according to this law, the amount of heat transferred from a cold body must be equal to the amount of heat received by a hot body. The first law also does not prohibit the transformation of internal energy into mechanical energy. Therefore, the first law of thermodynamics does not determine the direction of the process. The second law of thermodynamics determines the direction in which the process takes place. When an unbalanced state occurs in a closed system, processes that return it to a state of thermodynamic equilibrium occur. According to the second law of thermodynamics, a closed system tends towards the maximum entropy, i.e. the state of equilibrium with the highest degree of disorder.

CONCLUSION

The solution of equilibrium states in closed systems was explained using simple examples presented in the article. It was shown that the concepts of reversible and irreversible processes can be expressed in simple language. It was explained with the help of examples that the degree of disorder in the system consists of the statistical content of the concept of entropy. It was emphasized with the help

of relevant examples that real irreversible processes can occur in closed systems in the direction of system entropy increase.

The first basis of classical thermodynamics is the expression of the law of conservation of energy in thermal processes, which does not indicate the direction of the processes. The second law of thermodynamics, defined by the concept of entropy, is an important law that determines the direction of processes. The second law of thermodynamics is considered one of the greatest scientific discoveries of the 19th century, and the full delivery of its content to students ensures that they have perfect knowledge of natural phenomena. This article contains important information on the study of the laws of balanced thermodynamics in higher physics education, and it will be appropriate to use it in the educational process.

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